

IBPG - Darwin

The Institute of Biopaleogeography
named under Charles R. Darwin

IBPG 24 (2024) 1-70

E-ISSN 2956-4573

Cultural and contemplative expedition by the natural beauty of the Yellowstone National Park, Wyoming State, U.S.

Fabio Rossano Dario^{1,2,a} & Maria Cristina Veiga De Vincenzo^{2,b}

¹The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin,
Złocieniec, District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

²Ploia Agronomia, Ecologia e Meio Ambiente,
Rua Leonardo Mota, 66 - São Paulo-SP, ZIP 05586-090, Brazil

^{a,b}E-mail address: fabiorossano@hotmail.com , crisvincenzo@hotmail.com

The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin

Publisher's Address:

Scientific Publishing House DARWIN at The Institute
22, Adama Mickiewicza Street, 78-520 Złocieniec,
District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

Cite of this article:

Fabio Rossano Dario, Maria Cristina Veiga De Vincenzo. Cultural and contemplative expedition by the natural beauty of the Yellowstone National Park, Wyoming State, U.S. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin 24 (2024) 1-70*

ABSTRACT

This paper is a photographic summary of a scientific and touristic expedition carried out in August 2011 in Wyoming State, U.S. to know the natural beauties of the different ecosystems and the structure of the Yellowstone National Park. The photos show some of the Park and wilderness areas structures, important geological formations, and some of the species of flora and fauna registered.

Keywords: National Park, Yellowstone, tourism, environment, ecology

INTRODUCTION

Yellowstone National Park is located in the western United States (**Photos 1, 2**). Approximately 96 percent of the land area of Yellowstone is located within the state of Wyoming. The remaining area is in the states of Montana and Idaho (**Figure 1**). Yellowstone was the first national park in the U.S., created in 1872.

Figure 1. Localization of the Yellowstone National Park, US. (<https://www.usgs.gov>)

The name Yellowstone has been known since 1805 because the Native Americans were referring to yellow sandstones that incredibly stand out along the banks of the Yellowstone.

The park is known for its wildlife and its many geothermal features, especially the Old Faithful geyser, one of its most popular. While it represents many types of biomes, the subalpine forest is the most abundant.

Figure 2. Localization of the Yellowstone National Park, US. Source: U.S. Geological Survey (<https://www.usgs.gov>)

Yellowstone National Park has an area of about 9.000 km², with lakes, canyons, rivers, and mountain ranges. Yellowstone Lake is one of the largest high-elevation lakes in North America and is inserted over the Yellowstone Caldera, the largest supervolcano on the American continent. The Yellowstone Caldera is considered a dormant volcano. More than half

of the world's geysers and hydrothermal features are in Yellowstone National Park, "fueled by this ongoing volcanism" [1].

The incredible Yellowstone National Park is one of the better-preserved large ecosystems in the Earth's northern temperate zone. In 1978, Yellowstone was named a UNESCO World Heritage Site. The main objective of this scientific and touristic expedition, realized in August 2011 was to know the natural beauties of Yellowstone National Park, as well as to know the Park Service and the structure of this important park (**Figure 2**), identifying and photographing the natural riches accessible to our lens and the main plant and animal species that we saw.

Yellowstone National Park is a rich natural environment, of incredible biological richness, with thousands of species, including mammals, birds, fish, reptiles, amphibians, and insects, some several that are either endangered or threatened. In the forests and grasslands of this Park also live unique species of plants. Yellowstone National Park is the largest megafauna location in the United States, where live grizzly bears, cougars, wolves, herds of bison, and elk. The Yellowstone Park bison herd is the oldest, and largest public bison herd in the United States. "The landscape of Yellowstone is the result of various geological processes over the last 150 million years, where the Earth's crust has been compressed, pulled apart, glaciated, eroded, and subjected to volcanism", and this geologic activity formed mountains, canyons, and plateaus [2, 3].

"Mammoth Hot Springs is a large complex of hot springs on a hill of travertine in Yellowstone National Park. It was created over thousands of years as hot water from the spring cooled and deposited calcium carbonate. Because of the huge amount of geothermal vents, travertine flourishes. The hot water that feeds Mammoth comes from Norris Geyser Basin after traveling underground via a fault line that runs through limestone and roughly parallel to the Norris-to-Mammoth Road. The limestone from rock formations along the fault is the source of the calcium carbonate. Shallow circulation along this corridor allows Norris's superheated water to slightly cool before surfacing at Mammoth, generally at about 80 °C. Algae living in the warm pools have tinted the travertine shades of brown, orange, red, and green" [4] (**Photos 3-22**).

Yellowstone National Park is the big attraction of the Yellowstone ecosystem, a region that also includes Grand Teton National Park, and adjacent National Forests (**Photos 23, 24**). We can observe along the Yellowstone River, three spectacular sights of the Lower, Upper, and Crystal Falls. Each was formed by the river's flow over "progressively softer, less resistant rock". The Upper Falls of the Grand Canyon of Yellowstone are smaller than their lower counterpart. It has about 30 meters of fall. Its beauty and the scenic power of the surroundings are impressive (**Photos 27-39**). About 90 meters, the Lower Falls is the tallest waterfall in the Yellowstone. It is more than twice the size of Niagara Falls (**Photos 40-60**). Way back in 1870, a member of the Washburn party, Mr. N.P. Langford described the Lower Falls of the Grand Canyon of Yellowstone in this way: "A grander scene than the lower cataract of the Yellowstone was never witnessed by mortal eyes", a poetic way to say that this waterfall is a must-stop spot on a visit by Yellowstone National Park.

The coloration of the Grand Canyon of Yellowstone is what catches our attention the most, due to its scenic beauty. The brightly colored part of the Canyon is about five kilometers long with an average depth of 230 meters and a width of 460 meters. At the upper end are the two waterfalls known as the Upper and Lower Falls. "The colors white, yellow, orange, red, lavender, pink, and many others in varying tints with yellow predominating, are blended in the fluted and pinnacled walls in a natural and unpatterned manner that makes them extremely

attractive. The whole view is framed in the green of a lodgepole forest (*Pinus contorta*)" [5, 6]. "The colors in the rocks are largely due to traces of iron or other metallic oxides in various amounts and stages of oxidation and hydration. The color and disintegration of the rock have been brought about largely through the agency of hot gases and hot water, for this is the site of a former hot spring and geyser basin in fact, hot springs, fumaroles, and miniature geysers are still present in the Canyon" [6].

"According to historian Hiram Martin Chittenden (1858-1917), the river took its name from the canyon walls and later the Yellowstone region included the headwaters of the river. He says in effect that the early Indian tribes referred to the river that had "the yellow, nearly vertical walls." The French trappers before they had seen the canyon translated the Indian name to Roche Jaune and Pierre Jaune, meaning Yellow Rock and Yellow Stone; and now usage establishes the name, Yellowstone. Further than this, little is known about the name, though it seems likely that the Indians referred to were Sioux tribes, as Chittenden suggests, for the Crow Indians called it the Elk River" [6].

"A geyser is a spring characterized by an intermittent discharge of water ejected turbulently and accompanied by steam. As a fairly rare phenomenon, the formation of geysers is due to particular hydrogeological conditions that exist only in a few places on Earth" [7]. "Generally, all geyser field sites are located near active volcanic areas, and the geyser effect is due to the proximity of magma. Generally, surface water works its way down to an average depth of around 2,000 meters where it contacts hot rocks. The resultant boiling of the pressurized water results in the geyser effect of hot water and steam spraying out of the geyser's surface vent" [8].

Yellowstone National Park preserves a large number of hot springs, mudpots, geysers, and fumaroles. More than 10,000 hydrothermal features are found in Yellowstone, of which more than 500 are geysers. Discovered in 1870 by the Washburn Expedition (led by Henry D. Washburn and Nathaniel P. Langford, explored in 1870 the northwestern of Wyoming, which two years later became Yellowstone National Park), Old Faithful geyser was named for its frequent eruptions, which number more than a million since Yellowstone became the park, in 1872. It is located in Yellowstone's Upper Geyser Basin. The geyser-viewing area is accessible with bench seating, parking, and a visitor center. Old Faithful can vary in height from 30-50 meters, and the eruptions normally last between 1.5 to 5 minutes [9-12] (**Photos 61-78**).

Hot springs are the most common hydrothermal features in Yellowstone. Superheated water cools as it reaches the surface, sinks, and is replaced by hotter water from below. This circulation prevents water from reaching the temperature needed to set off an eruption. Hydrothermal features are also habitats in which microscopic organisms survive and thrive. They are called thermophiles (heat lovers). They are too small to be seen with the naked eye, but trillions grouped are visible as a beautiful manifestation of colors. They are nourished by energy and chemical building blocks. Colorless and yellow thermophiles grow in the hottest water, while orange, brown, and green thermophiles grow in cooler waters [13-16].

Morning Glory Pool was always a favorite destination for early visitors. It was named in the 1880s for its remarkable likeness to its namesake flower (*Ipomoea nil*), both a deep blue. Unfortunately, this beautiful pool that nature created radiating a deep blue was a victim to vandalism: over the years humans have thrown in tons of coins, and all variety of trash into the pool. Much of this debris became embedded in the sides and vent of the spring, which reduced the water circulation and thus the water temperature. Then, cooler temperatures allow orange- and yellow-colored bacteria to thrive. Therefore, orange and yellow are currently its

predominant colors. Morning Glory Pool has an average temperature of 70°C and an average pH of 7.6 [17-21] (**Photos 79-89**).

A mud volcano is a conical structure of clayey mud, described by early explorers as a “most repulsive and terrifying site.” When Nathaniel P. Langford, the first superintendent of Yellowstone, visited in 1870, he saw “a seething, bubbling mass of mud.” The areas surrounding the Mud Volcano vent and the other major vent near Old Faithful are called resurgent domes. This entire region of Mud Volcano can be appreciated by walking along the very well-marked trails. Several types of outcrops constitute very attractions [22-24] (**Photos 91-96**). Yellowstone is known for its geysers, hot springs, fumaroles, and mud pots, and it was these attractions that led to the creation of this National Park. In the Boiling River, you can immerse yourself in hot waters. It is a stream of hot water from the Gardner River. The tourists put rocks to create a small swimming pool where the 60 °C water mixes with the cold river [25] (**Photos 97-100**).

The Grand Prismatic Spring in Yellowstone National Park is the largest hot spring in the United States and the third largest in the world. It was noted by geologists working in the Hayden Geological Survey of 1871 and named by them for its magnificent coloration. Its colors match most of those seen in the rainbow: red, orange, yellow, green, and blue. These incredible colors are the result of microbial action and depend on the quantity of chlorophyll and the water temperature. In the summer, the coloring tends to be orange and red, whereas in the winter is usually dark green. The center of the pool is sterile due to extreme heat, being the deep blue color of the water in the center of the pool results from the intrinsic blue color of water [26, 27] (**Photos 101-114**).

Yellowstone National Park is considered the world's largest intact ecosystem in the northern temperate zone and is home to a key field observation site for the National Ecological Observatory Network. Over 69,000 species of trees and other vascular plants are native to the park. Of the eight conifer tree species documented, Lodgepole Pine (*Pinus contorta*) forests cover 80% of the total forested areas. Other conifers, such as Subalpine Fir (*Abies lasiocarpa*), Engelmann Spruce (*Picea engelmannii*), Rocky Mountain Douglas-fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii*), and Whitebark Pine (*Pinus albicaulis*), are found in scattered groves throughout the Park [28-39].

There are almost 60 species of mammals in Yellowstone, including the Rocky Mountain wolf (*Canis lupus irremotus*), coyote (*Canis latrans*), the Canadian lynx (*Lynx canadensis*), cougars (*Puma concolor*), and both: black (*Ursus americanus*) and grizzly bears (*Ursus arctos horribilis*). Other large mammals include the bison (*Bison bison* - **Photo 62**, often referred to as buffalo), elk (*Cervus elaphus* - **Photo 64**), moose (*Alces alces*), mule deer (*Odocoileus hemionus*), white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*), mountain goat (*Oreamnos americanus*), pronghorn (*Antilocapra americana* - **Photo 99**), and bighorn sheep (*Ovis canadensis*). The Yellowstone Park bison herd is the largest public herd of American bison in the United States (**Photos 25, 26**). Bison once numbered between 30 and 60 million individuals throughout North America, and Yellowstone remains one of their last strongholds. Population figures for elk (*Cervus elaphus*) are more than 30,000, the largest population of any large mammal species in Yellowstone [40-86].

"That the inspirational quality of such scenery is unlimited was expressed by a number of early travelers. Nathaniel Pitt Langford (1832-1911), a member of an early exploring party, wrote: "As I took in this scene, I realized my own littleness, my helplessness, my dread exposure to destruction, my inability to cope with or even comprehend the mighty architecture of nature."

Then, "the two grand falls of the Yellowstone form a fitting completion to this stupendous climax of wonders. They impart life, power, light, and majesty to an assemblage of elements, which without them would be the most gloomy and horrible solitude in nature. Their eternal anthem, echoing from canon, with rapture at the iris-crowned curtains of fleecy foam as they plunge into gulfs enveloped in mist and spray. The stillness which held your senses spellbound, as you peered into the dismal depths of the canyon below, is now broken by the uproar of waters; the terror it inspired is superseded by admiration and astonishment, and the scene, late so painful from its silence, is now animate with joy and revelry"[6].

The photos presented in this report were taken by Fabio Rossano Dario, and Cristina De Vincenzo, using a cellphone and digital photo camera Canon PowerShot.

CONCLUSIONS

On a trip to the U.S., is essential to know the National Parks, because the park system in the U.S. is very well organized and includes National Parks, National Forests, and Wilderness Areas, with several parameters related to the physical infrastructure to the well-being of the visitors and comfort as well.

Yellowstone National Park has a great wealth of landscapes full of natural beauty, with its extraordinary variety of rivers, canyons, and mountains. These natural environments host a wide variety of plant and animal species, some endemic, others endangered, and many of which are still unknown. The park is also known for many geothermal features, especially the geysers.

References

- [1] J.B. Johnson, J.F. Anderson, R.E. Anthony, M. Sciotto. Detecting geyser activity with infrasound. *Journal of Volcanology, and Geothermal Research* 256 (2013) 105-117
- [2] D. James, M. Fouch, R.W. Carlson, J. Roth. Slab fragmentation, edge flow, and the origin of the Yellowstone hotspot track. *Earth, and Planetary Science Letters* 311(1-2) (2011) 124-135
- [3] Y. Zhou. Anomalous mantle transition zone beneath the Yellowstone hotspot track. *Nature Geoscience* 11(6) (2018) 449-453.
- [4] B.B. Carr, C. Jaworowski, H.P. Heasler. Mapping change at Mammoth Hot Springs using aerial photographs and visual observations. *Yellowstone Science* 18(3) (2010) 15-22
- [5] J.A. Antos, R. Parish. Dynamics of an old-growth, fire-initiated, subalpine forest in southern interior British Columbia: Tree size, age, and spatial structure. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 32 (2002) 1935-1946
- [6] C.M. Bauer. The Grand Canyon of the Yellowstone. *Yellowstone Nature Notes* 14(3-4) (1937)
- [7] H. Heasler, C. Jaworowski. Hydrothermal monitoring of Norris Geyser Basin, Yellowstone National Park, USA, using airborne thermal infrared imagery. *Geothermics* 72 (2018) 24-46

- [8] S. Lewin. Instant Egghead: How do geysers erupt over and over?. *Scientific American* 312(5) (2015) 27
- [9] C. Jaworowski, H.P. Heasler, C.C. Hardy, L.P. Queen. Control of hydrothermal fluids by natural fractures at Norris Geyser Basin. *Yellowstone Science* 14(1) (2006) 13-23
- [10] C. Jaworowski, H.P. Heasler, C.M. Neale, S. Sivarajan. Using thermal infrared imagery and LiDAR in Yellowstone geyser basins. *Yellowstone Science* 18(1) (2010) 8-19
- [11] C. Jaworowski, H.P. Heasler, C.M.U. Neale, S. Sivarajan, A. Masih. Temporal and spatial variations of the Hot Spring Basin hydrothermal system, Yellowstone National Park, USA. *Remote Sensing* 5(12) (2013) 6587-6610
- [12] D. Shean. Norris Geyser Basin's dynamic hydrothermal features. *Yellowstone Science* 14(4) (2006) 24-28
- [13] Y. Dong, R.A. Sanford, W.P. Inskeep, V. Srivastava, V. Bulone, C.J. Fields, P.M. Yau, M. Sivaguru, D. Ahrén, K.W. Fouke, J. Weber, C.R. Werth, I.K. Cann, K.M. Keating, R.S. Khetani, A.G. Hernandez, C. Wright, M. Band, B.S. Imai, G.A. Fried, B.W. Fouke. Physiology, Metabolism, and fossilization of Hot-Spring filamentous microbial mats. *Astrobiology* 19(12) (2019) 1442-1458
- [14] F. Kasting, L. Siefert. Life and the evolution of Earth's atmosphere. *Science*, 296(5570) (2002) 1066-1068
- [15] T. Peglar. Grand Prismatic Spring at Yellowstone's Midway Geyser Basin. *Yellowstone National Park Trips* (2017)
- [16] M. Klingeberg, F. Hashwa, G. Antranikian. Properties of extremely thermostable proteases from anaerobic hyperthermophilic bacteria. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 34 (1991) 715-719
- [17] P. Nugent, J.A. Shaw, M. Vollmer. Colors of thermal pools at Yellowstone National Park. *Applied Optics* 54(4) (2015) 128-139
- [18] D.M. Ward, M.J. Ferris, S.C. Nold, M.M. Bateson. A natural view of microbial biodiversity within hot spring cyanobacterial mat communities. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews* 62 (1998) 1353-1370
- [19] R.T. Papke, N.B. Ramsing, M.M. Bateson, D.M. Ward. Geographical isolation in hot spring cyanobacteria. *Environmental Microbiology* 5 (2003) 650-659
- [20] .H. Segrer, S. Burggraf, G. Fiala, G. Huber, R. Huber, U. Pley, K.O. Stetter. Life in hot springs and hydrothermal vents. *Origins of Life and Evolution of Biospheres* 23 (1993) 77-90
- [21] C.R. Lehr, S.D. Frank, T.B. Norris, S. D'Imperio, A.V. Kalinin, J.A. Toplin, R.W. Castenholz, T.R. McDermott. *Cyandia* (Cyanidiales) population diversity and dynamics in an acid-sulfate-chloride spring in Yellowstone National Park. *Journal of Phycology* 43 (2007) 3-14
- [22] C.A. Finn, P.A. Bedrosian, W.S. Holbrook, E. Auken, B.R. Bloss, J. Crosbie. Geophysical imaging of the Yellowstone hydrothermal plumbing system. *Nature* 603 (2022) 643-647

- [23] J. Holt, J.C. Pechmann, K.D. Koper. Recalibration of the local magnitude (ML) scale for earthquakes in the Yellowstone volcanic region. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 112(2) (2022) 905-920
- [24] S. Hurwitz, J.B. Lowenstern. Dynamics of the Yellowstone hydrothermal system. *Reviews of Geophysics* 52 (2014) 375-411
- [25] L.A. Morgan, W.C.P. Shanks, J.B. Lowenstern, J.M. Farrell, J.E. Robinson. Geologic field-trip guide to the volcanic and hydrothermal landscape of the Yellowstone Plateau: U.S. *Geological Survey Scientific Investigations Report* (2017) 100 p.
- [26] L.L. Ahnke. Lipid biomarker and carbon isotopic signatures for stromatolite-forming, microbial mat communities and Phormidium cultures from Yellowstone National Park. *Geobiology* 2(1) (2004) 31-47
- [27] S. Kumar, R. Nussinov. How do thermophilic proteins deal with heat? *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences* 58 (2001) 1216-1233
- [28] R. Daubenmire. Forest vegetation of northern Idaho and adjacent Washington and its bearing on concepts of vegetation classification. *Ecological Monographs* 22 (1952) 309-330
- [29] S.J. Eis. Development of white spruce and alpine fir seedlings on cutover areas in the central interior of British Columbia. *Forestry Chronicle* 41 (1965) 419-431
- [30] L.J. Herring, R.G. McMinn. Natural and advanced regeneration of Engelmann spruce and subalpine fir compared 21 years after site treatment. *Forestry Chronicle* 56 (1980) 55-57
- [31] R.R. Alexander. Cutting methods in relation to resource use in central Rocky Mountain spruce-fir forests. *Journal of Forestry* 75 (1977) 395-400
- [32] B.H. Luckman, L.A. Jozsa, P.J. Murphy. Living seven-hundred-year-old *Picea engelmannii* and *Pinus albicaulis* in the Canadian Rockies. *Arctic and Alpine Research* 16(4) (1984) 419-442
- [33] H.J. Oosting, J.F. Reed. Virgin spruce-fir of the medicine bow mountains, Wyoming. *Ecological Monographs* 22(2) (1952) 69-91
- [34] D.L. Noble, R.R. Alexander. Environmental factors affecting natural regeneration of Engelmann spruce in the central Rocky Mountains. *Forest Science* 23 (1977) 420-429
- [35] P. Li, W.T. Adams. Range-wide patterns of allozyme variation in Douglas-fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii*). *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 19 (1989) 149-161
- [36] R.A. Monserud. Height growth and site index curves for inland Douglas-fir based on stem analysis data and forest habitat type. *Forest Science* 30(4) (1984) 943-965
- [37] P.J. Bartlein, C. Whitlock, S.L. Shafer. Future climate in the Yellowstone National Park region and its potential impact on vegetation. *Conservation Biology* 11 (1997) 782-792
- [38] A.D. Bower, S.N. Aitken. Ecological genetics and seed transfer guidelines for *Pinus albicaulis* (Pinaceae). *American Journal of Botany* 95 (2008) 66-76

- [39] L.P. Breuderle, D.F. Tomback, K.K. Kelly, R.C. Hardwick. Population genetic structure in a bird-dispersed pine, *Pinus albicaulis* (Pinaceae). *Canadian Journal of Botany* 76 (1998) 83-90
- [40] S.L. Eggeman, M. Hebblewhite, J. Cunningham, K. Hamlin. Fluctuating asymmetry in elk *Cervus Elaphus* antlers is unrelated to environmental conditions in the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem. *Biological Sciences Faculty Publications* 285 (2009) 299-309
- [41] M.B. Coughenour, F.J. Singer. Elk population processes in Yellowstone National Park under the policy of natural regulation. *Ecological Applications* 6(2) (1996) 573-593
- [42] A.J. Bath, T. Buchanan. Attitudes of interest groups in Wyoming toward wolf restoration in Yellowstone National Park. *Wildlife Society Bulletin* 17 (1989) 519-525
- [43] J.E. Swenson, F. Sandegren, S. Brunberg, P. Wabakken. Winter den abandonment by brown bears, *Ursus arctos*: causes and consequences. *Wildlife Biology* 3 (1997) 35-38
- [44] B.N. McLellan, F.W. Hovey. Natal dispersal of grizzly bears. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 79 (2001) 838-844
- [45] D.J. Mattson. Use of ungulates by Yellowstone grizzly bears *Ursus arctos*. *Biological Conservation* 81 (1997) 161-177
- [46] J.D.C. Linnell, J.E. Swenson, R. Andersen, B. Barnes. How vulnerable are denning bears to disturbance? *Wildlife Society Bulletin* 28 (2000) 400-413
- [47] W.B. Ballard, R. Farnell, R.O. Stephenson. Long distance movement by Gray Wolves, *Canis lupus*. *Canadian Field-Naturalist* 97 (1983) 333
- [48] L.D. Mech. *Canis lupus*. *Mammalian Species* 37 (1974) 1-6
- [49] R.O. Peterson, R.E. Page. The rise and fall of Isle Royale wolves, 1975-1986. *Journal of Mammalogy* 69 (1988) 89-99
- [50] D.H. Pletscher, R.R. Ream, D.K. Boyd, M.W. Fairchild, K.E. Kunkel. Population dynamics of a recolonizing wolf population. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 61 (1997) 459-465
- [51] E. Post, R.O. Peterson, N.C. Stenseth, B.E. McClaren. Ecosystem consequences of wolf behavioral response to climate. *Nature* 401 (1999) 905-907
- [52] S.H. Fritts, L.D. Mech. Dynamics, movements, and feeding ecology of a newly protected wolf population in northwestern Minnesota. *Wildlife Monographs* 80 (1981) 1-79
- [53] E.E. Bangs, S.H. Fritts, J.A. Fontaine, D.W. Smith, K.M. Murphy, C.M. Mack, C.C. Niemeyer. Status of gray wolf restoration in Montana, Idaho, and Wyoming. *Wildlife Society Bulletin* 26 (1998) 785-798
- [54] A.B. Bubenik, B.A. Pond. Principles of sociobiological modeling of moose (*Alces alces andersonii*) of the North American taiga. *Alces* 1 (1992) 29-51
- [55] A.W. Franzmann, P.D. Arneson, J.L. Oldemeyer. Daily winter pellet groups and beds of Alaskan moose. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 40 (1976) 374-375

- [56] S.D. Kovach, C.C. Schwartz, R.L. Willis, T.H. Spraker. Modeling moose populations for management decision making in Alaska. *Alces* 34 (1998) 125-138
- [57] J.J. Craighead, G. Atwell, B.W. O’Gara. Elk migration in and near Yellowstone National Park. *Wildlife Monographs* 29 (1972) 1-48
- [58] E.E. Bangs, S.E. Fritts. Reintroducing the gray wolf to central Idaho and Yellowstone National Park. *Wildlife Society Bulletin* 24 (1996) 402-413
- [59] T.R. Thomas, L.R. Irby. Habitat use and movement patterns by migrating mule deer in southeastern Idaho. *Northwest Science* 64 (1990) 19-27
- [60] H. Sawyer, F. Lindzey, D. McWhirter. Mule deer and pronghorn migration in western Wyoming. *Wildlife Society Bulletin* 33 (2005) 1266-1273
- [61] C.L. Wambolt. Mule deer and elk foraging preference for 4 sage-brush taxa. *Journal of Range Management* 49 (1996) 499-503
- [62] C.L. Wambolt. Sagebrush and ungulate relationships on Yellowstone’s northern range. *Wildlife Society Bulletin* 26 (1998) 429-437
- [63] J. Berger, P.B. Stacey, L. Bellis, M.P. Johnson. A mammalian predator-prey imbalance: grizzly bears and wolf extinction affect avian Neotropical migrants. *Ecological Applications* 11 (2001) 947-960
- [64] W.J. Ripple, E.J. Larsen, R.A. Renkin, D.W. Smith. Trophic cascades among wolves, elk and aspen on Yellowstone National Park’s northern range. *Biological Conservation* 102 (2001) 227-234
- [65] D.W. Smith, L.D. Mech, M. Meagher, W.E. Clark, R. Jaffe, M.K. Phillips, J.A. Mack. Wolf bison interactions in Yellowstone National Park. *Journal of Mammalogy* 81 (2000) 1128-1135.
- [66] J. Monje-Nájera, B. Morera-Brenes. Why is the coyote (*Canis latrans*) expanding its range? A critique of the deforestation hypothesis. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 35(1) (1987)169-171
- [67] T.E. Chubbs, F.R. Phillips. An apparent longevity record for Canada lynx, *Lynx canadensis*, in Labrador. *Canadian Field-Naturalist* 107 (1993) 367-368
- [68] J.A. Litvaitis, D. Kingman Jr., E. Orff. Status of lynx in New Hampshire. *Transactions of the Northeast Section of the Wildlife Society* 48 (1991) 70-75
- [69] A.K. Fuller, D.J. Harrison. Movement paths reveal scale-dependent habitat decisions by Canada lynx. *Journal of Mammalogy* 91 (2010) 1269-1279
- [70] G.M. Koehler. Population and habitat characteristics of lynx and snowshoe hares in north central Washington. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 68 (1990) 845-851
- [71] N.P. McCann, R.A. Moen. Mapping potential core areas for lynx (*Lynx canadensis*) using pellet counts from snowshoe hares (*Lepus americanus*) and satellite imagery. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 89 (2011) 509-516

- [72] F.J. Singer, A. Harting, K.K. Symonds, M.B. Coughenour. Density dependence, compensation, and environmental effects on elk calf mortality in Yellowstone National Park. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 61 (1997) 12-25
- [73] L.L. Eberhardt, P.J. White, R.A. Garrott, D.B. Houston. A seventy-year history of trends in Yellowstone's northern elk herd. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 71 (2007) 594-602
- [74] J.P. Beckmann, J. Berger. Rapid ecological and behavioural changes in carnivores: the responses of black bears (*Ursus americanus*) to altered food. *Journal of Zoology* 261 (2003) 207-212
- [75] E.M. Addison, M.J. Pybus, H.J. Rietveld. Helminth and arthropod parasites of black bear, *Ursus americanus*, in central Ontario. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 56 (1978) 122-2126
- [76] J.A. Allen. The black bear of Labrador. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History* 28 (1910) 1-6
- [77] G.L. Alt. Rate of growth and size of Pennsylvania black bears. *Pennsylvania Game News* 51(12) (1980) 7-17
- [78] D.L. Garshelis, H.B. Quigley, C.R. Villarubia. Diel movements of black bears in the southern Appalachians. *Ursus* 5 (1983) 11-19
- [79] L.A. Ayres, L.S. Chow, D.M. Graber. Black bear activity patterns and human induced modifications in Sequoia National Park. *Ursus* 6 (1986) 151-154
- [80] E.C. Hellgren, M.R. Vaughan. Denning ecology of black bears in a southeastern wetland. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 53 (1989) 347-353
- [81] W.F. Kasworm, T.L. Manley. Road and trail influences on grizzly bears and black bears in northwest Montana. *Ursus* 8 (1990) 79-84
- [82] J.D. Clark, D.L. Clapp, K.G. Smith. Black bear habitat use in relation to food availability in the Interior Highlands of Arkansas. *Ursus* 9(1) (1994) 309-318
- [83] G.B. Kolenosky. Reproductive biology of black bears in east-central Ontario. *Ursus* 8 (1990) 385-392
- [84] T.E. Reimchen. Nocturnal foraging behaviour of black bears, *Ursus americanus*, on Moresby Island, British Columbia. *Canadian Field-Naturalist* 112 (1998) 446-450
- [85] B.J. Wear, R. Eastridge, J.D. Clark. Factors affecting settling, survival, and viability of black bears reintroduced to Felsenthal National Wildlife Refuge, Arkansas. *Wildlife Society Bulletin* 33 (2005) 1363-1374
- [86] S.E. Tardiff, J.A. Stanford. Grizzly bear digging: effects on subalpine meadow plants in relation to mineral nitrogen availability. *Ecology* 79 (1998) 2219-2228

Photo 1. Yellowstone National Park was the first national park in the U.S., created in 1872. Located in the western United States, it is known for its wildlife, and its many geothermal features, especially the geysers, a thermal spring that erupts periodically, releasing a column of hot water, and steam.

Photo 2. The Roosevelt Arch in Gardiner, Montana, at the north entrance of the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 3. Mammoth Hot Springs is a large complex of hot springs on a hill of travertine in Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 4. This mammoth-sized hot spring is simply named Mammoth Hot Springs because of its impressive size. Unfortunately, not because fossils of an ancient mammoth were found at the site.

Photo 5. Many trails into Yellowstone's wilderness begin in the Mammoth Hot Springs area.

Photo 6. Crystallized calcium carbonate terraces in Mammoth Hot Springs.

Photo 7. Mammoth Hot Springs is a surficial expression of the deep volcanic forces at work in Yellowstone.

Photo 8. The limestone from rock formations is the source of the calcium carbonate in Mammoth Hot Springs.

Photo 9. Mammoth Hot Springs is one of the most surreal regions of the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 10. The travertine terraces in Mammoth Hot Springs in Yellowstone National Park hosts thermophilic Cyanobacteria.

Photo 11. Tourists are sometimes confused about the shifting activity of the hot springs and disappointed when a favorite spring appears to have died ...

Photo 12. ... it is important to know that the location of springs and the rate of flow changes constantly.

Photo 13. Algae living in the warm pools in Mammoth Hot Springs have tinted the travertine shades of brown, orange, red...

Photo 14. ... and green.

Photo 15. Mammoth Hot Springs is one of the most unique thermal basins in Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 16. Travertine formations grow much more rapidly due to the softer nature of limestone. As hot water rises through limestone, large quantities of rock are dissolved by the hot water, and a white chalky mineral is deposited on the surface.

Photo 17. Mammoth Hot Springs was created over thousands of years as hot water from the spring cooled and deposited calcium carbonate.

Photo 18. Thermal activity in Mammoth Hot Springs is extensive both over time and distance.

Photo 19. Mammoth Hot Springs It is one of the best attractions of Yellowstone National Park. This landscape of the greater Yellowstone ecosystem is the result of various geological processes over the last 150 million years.

Photo 20. Killdeer (*Charadrius vociferus*), is a large plover found in the Americas. It primarily feeds on insects, although other invertebrates and seeds are eaten. It forages almost exclusively in fields, especially those with short vegetation and standing water.

Photo 21. Sign indicating the danger of walking off the trail.

Photo 22. Because of the huge number of geothermal vents, travertine flourishes in Mammoth Hot Springs.

Photo 23. The landscape of the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem is the result of various geological processes over the last 150 million years.

Photo 24. Earth's crust has been compressed, pulled apart, glaciated, eroded, and subjected to volcanism. This geologic activity was responsible for the formation of mountains, canyons, and plateaus that define the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 25. The Yellowstone Park bison herd is the oldest, and largest public bison herd in the United States.

Photo 26. The Yellowstone Park bison herd is believed to be one of only four free-roaming and genetically pure herds on public lands in North America.

Photo 27. The Yellowstone River in Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 28. The Yellowstone Basin watershed contains a system of rivers, including the Yellowstone River. These rivers form tributaries to the Missouri River.

Photo 29. The Yellowstone River flows northward through Yellowstone National Park, feeding and draining Yellowstone Lake, then dropping over the Upper and Lower Yellowstone Falls at the head of the Grand Canyon of Yellowstone within the confines of the park.

Photo 30. Virtually every square foot of the Yellowstone National Park would fall into these three categories: plants, scenery, and wildlife.

Photo 31. Information board about the presence of osprey nests. The osprey (*Pandion haliaetus*) is a diurnal, fish-eating bird of prey with a cosmopolitan range.

Photo 32. An osprey nest with three babies was recorded during our hike in Yellowstone.

Photo 33. The trails are well maintained and safe, some with stairs or an incline, especially those that arrive at the foot of the waterfalls.

Photo 34. Walking along the trail leads to the less-visited profile view of Upper Falls.

Photo 35. Yellowstone National Park has many nice spots for meditation.

Photo 36. A trail following to the Upper Falls.

Photo 37. Approaching the very busy lookout right at the brink of the Upper Falls. The handrail ensures the safety of walkers in dangerous areas.

Photo 38. The great plant diversity creates a fascinating interplay of plant colors and structures. The waterfalls are surrounded by mountains and forests.

Photo 39. Upper Falls is a major waterfall of the Yellowstone River.

Photo 40. The trails in Yellowstone have many signposts and indications.

Photo 41. Lodgepole Pine forests cover 80% of the Park's total forested areas. Lodgepole pine (*Pinus contorta*) is a species that grows throughout the western U.S.

Photo 42. The whole view is framed in the green of a lodgepole forest.

Photo 43. The name Yellowstone was attributed as early as 1805 to Native Americans who were referring to yellow sandstones along the banks of the Yellowstone River in eastern Montana.

Photo 44. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 45. The early Indian tribes referred to the river that had "the yellow, nearly vertical walls".

Photo 46. Yellowstone is home to both grizzly bears and black bears. Safe traveling in bear country begins before you get on the trail. Learning about bears can help you avoid a confrontation.

Photo 47. Signposts are distributed along the trails. They were made of wood and were in perfect harmony with the environment.

Photo 48. The Yellowstone River is considered the principal tributary of the upper Missouri.

Photo 49. Over 69000 species of plants are native to the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 50. Dozens of species of flowering plants have been identified in Yellowstone, most of which bloom between May and September.

Photo 51. The Yellowstone River is the principal tributary of the upper Missouri River, approximately 1,114 km long, in the Western United States.

Photo 52. The landscape of the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem is the result of various geological processes over the last 150 million years.

Photo 53. The yellow-bellied marmot (*Marmota flaviventris*) is a diurnal rodent mammal, which spends most of its time on the ground and is quite easy to observe in Yellowstone.

Photo 54. A little of the story is told through the growth rings of a dead tree trunk. The oldest rings are towards the center of the trunk and the newest rings are on the outside layer closest to the bark. The light-colored rings represent wood that grew in the spring and early summer, while the dark rings represent wood that grew in the late summer and fall.

Photo 55. The iron ladder and handrail ensure the safety of walkers in dangerous areas.

Photo 56. Plunging within the depths of the Grand Canyon of the Yellowstone River.

Photo 57. “The colors white, yellow, orange, red, lavender, pink, and many others in varying tints with yellow predominating, are blended in the fluted and pinnacled walls in a natural and unpatterned manner that makes them extremely attractive” (C. Max Bauer).

Photo 58. “The color and disintegration of the rock has been brought about largely through the agency of hot gases and hot water, for this is the site of a former hot spring and geyser basin and in fact, hot springs, fumaroles, and miniature geysers are still present in the Canyon” (C. Max Bauer).

Photo 59. You can admire this beautiful waterfall from different views along the trails.

Photo 60. About 90 meters, the Lower Falls is the tallest waterfall in the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 61. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 62. Yellowstone National Park is the only place continuously inhabited by bison since prehistoric times, and the species numbers nearly 5,000.

Photo 63. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 64. Elk (*Cervus elaphus*) is the largest member of the deer family (Cervidae) in the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 65. Unlike most other national parks, boating is forbidden within Yellowstone National Park, leaving it with more than 400 miles of virtually unexplored rivers.

Photo 66. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 67. Yellowstone National Park preserves hot springs, geysers, mudpots, and fumaroles. Generally, all geyser field sites are located near active volcanic areas, and the geyser effect is due to the proximity of magma.

Photo 68. Hot springs are the most common hydrothermal features in Yellowstone. Superheated water cools as it reaches the surface, sinks, and is replaced by hotter water from below.

Photo 69. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 70. The majority of the world's active geysers are in the Upper Geyser Basin, Yellowstone, including Old Faithful.

Photo 71. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 72. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 73. Underground cracks form a natural plumbing system. Hot water rises through the plumbing to produce hot springs and geysers.

Photo 74. The heat for the hydrothermal features comes from Yellowstone's volcano.

Photo 75. Microbial mat in cooled geyser water.

Photo 76. Hot springs are formed when water from deep within the earth emerges through the cracks in its surface.

Photo 77. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 78. The world's most famous geyser, Old Faithful in Yellowstone, currently erupts around 20 times a day.

Photo 79. Hydrothermal features are also habitats in which microscopic organisms survive and thrive. Although they are too small to be seen with the naked eye, trillions are grouped and appear as masses of color.

Photo 80. Colorless and yellow thermophiles grow in the hottest water.

Photo 81. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 82. Orange, brown, and green thermophiles grow in cooler waters.

Photo 83. Tourists in Yellowstone National Park often take pictures of the beautiful hot springs, capturing the rainbow coloration provided by the spring's large groupings of microbial life.

Photo 84. The park's thermophilic features are ideal locations to explore the fundamental questions regarding life under extreme conditions.

Photo 85. The different thermophilic microbes present within the spring all have their own desired temperatures, and they cannot tolerate much cooler or warmer conditions.

Photo 86. Going on a hike is a wonderful way to experience some of the rich natural beauty present in national parks, and protected reserves, such as the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 87. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 88. Morning Glory Pool is a hot spring in the Yellowstone Upper Geyser Basin. This old blue pool became a victim of vandalism. Over the years humans have thrown tons of coins, and a variety of trash into the pool. Today, cooler temperatures allow orange and yellow-colored bacteria to thrive.

Photo 89. Observing the natural beauties of the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 90. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 91. Mud Volcano is near the greatest uplift and sinking of the Yellowstone Caldera floor. Many faults converge here, and earthquakes are common.

Photo 92. This entire region of Mud Volcano must be appreciated by walking along the marked trails.

Photo 93. Dozens of species of flowering plants have been identified in Yellowstone, most of which bloom between May and September.

Photo 94. Flowers of Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 95. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 96. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 97. The Boiling River is a stream of hot water. It is the quintessential Yellowstone hot springs swimming experience.

Photo 98. Boiling River, you can immerse yourself in hot waters. It is a stream of hot water from the Gardner River. The tourists put rocks to create a small swimming pool where the 60^C water mixes with the cold river.

Photo 99. The pronghorn (*Antilocapra americana*) is a species of artiodactyl mammal to interior western, and central North America. It is the only surviving member of the family Antilocapridae.

Photo 100. Our tents at the Yellowstone campsite.

Photo 101. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 102. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 103. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 104. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 105. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 106. The Grand Prismatic Spring in Yellowstone National Park is the largest hot spring in the United States and the third largest in the world. A closer look at *Calothrix*, responsible for the Grand Prismatic Spring's brown bacterial mats, as well as the orange mats that are primarily derived from *Phormidium*.

Photo 107. Grand Prismatic Spring was noted by geologists working in the Hayden Geological Survey of 1871, and named by them for its striking coloration. The mats produce colors ranging from green to red; the amount of color in the microbial mats depends on the ratio of chlorophyll to carotenoids and on the temperature gradient in the runoff.

Photo 108. Grand Prismatic Hot Spring is the most photographed thermal feature in Yellowstone National Park, U.S. Its colors match most of those seen in the rainbow dispersion of white light by an optical prism: red, orange, yellow, green, and blue. The bright, vivid colors in the spring are the result of microbial mats around the edges of the mineral-rich water.

Photo 109. Boardwalks allow visitors to safely approach the thermal features, such as the Grand Prismatic Spring.

Photo 110. Hot springs are the most common hydrothermal features in the Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 111. The deep blue color of the water in the center of the pool results from the intrinsic blue color of the water.

Photo 112. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 113. Yellowstone National Park.

Photo 114. The Bald Eagle (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*) is a large fish-eagle with a dark brown body and a distinctive white head and tail acquired at 4 to 5 years of age. It is found near large bodies of open water with an abundant food supply and old-growth trees for nesting like in Yellowstone.